

sulphon-sodio (or potassio) chloro (or bromo) amide (Todd, Fletcher, *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 350) with sodium or potassium cyanide and subsequent hydrolysis according to the following schemes respectively.

But by varying the reactants, or changing the mode of reactions in divergent ways, no such reaction could be brought about in any appreciable yield. Reacting alkyl sulphocyanide with an alkali metal salt of sulphanilamide, however, in presence of a phenolic solvent, the reaction proceeded as follows :—

The sulphanilyl (*p*-sulphonamidophenyl) guanidine (I), which is partly formed during the course of the reaction by the interaction of the sulphanilyl cyanamide formed, with unchanged sulphanilamide, can be easily separated out from the reaction mixture by partial acidification. The mother-liquor on complete acidification readily affords sulphanilyl cyanamide which crystallises from water in clusters of needles, m.p. 292°.

EXPERIMENTAL

Attempts to Synthesise p-Aminobenzene-sulphocyanamide

Sulphanilamide, as available in the market, was purified by crystallisation from water and the product melting at 164-66° was used throughout the course of the investigation.

p-Acetaminobenzene sulphonamide (5 g.), sodium bicarbonate (4g.) and water (50 c.c.) were mixed in a 100 c.c. conical flask. To this cyanogen bromide (3g.) was added and the whole thing shaken for 8 hours and left overnight at the room temperature. Next day it was filtered and washed with water. The residue melted at 215° and showed no depression in melting point when mixed with an authentic sample of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonamide. The filtrate on acidification yielded a white crystalline substance, which was also found to be *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonamide. Similarly, no condensation was brought about by reacting *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonamide with cyanogen bromide in boiling acetone, by refluxing with xylene in presence of potassium carbonate and copper bronze, nor in a sealed tube at 125-130° for 3 hours. Even the sodium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonamide failed to react with cyanogen bromide when refluxed for 4 hours in alcoholic suspension.

p-Acetaminobenzene sulphon-sodio (or potassio) chloro (or bromo) amide, prepared according to the method of Todd *et al.* could not also be condensed with sodium or potassium cyanide in aqueous, alcoholic or in any neutral solvent by any of the procedures as mentioned above.

Condensation of p-Aminobenzene-sulphonamide with Alkyl Sulphocyanide

Preparation of Sulphanilyl Cyanamide.—Sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide (9 parts) was taken in phenol (18 parts) and the mixture heated to 150°, ethyl sulphocyanide (4 parts) was gradually added to the mixture during the course of an hour. After that the whole thing was heated for 2 hours at 180°. The reaction mixture was then cooled and diluted with benzene when a solid separated out. This was dissolved in water and the solution partially neutralised with 2 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid when a solid again separated out (A). The mother-liquor was again neutralised with 2.6 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid under ice-cooling. Crystals, m.p. 280-85°, thus obtained were further purified by recrystallisation from water (charcoal) as needles, m.p. 292°. (Found: N, 21.5; S, 16.2. $C_7H_7O_2N_2S$ requires N, 21.3; S, 16.3 per cent).

The sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide (10.7 parts) in phenol (21 parts) was heated to 150° and methyl sulphocyanide (4 parts) gradually added to the mixture and the heating continued for 1 hour at 180°. The reaction mixture was cooled and diluted with benzene, filtered and a solid separated from which *p*-aminobenzene sulphonycyanamide, m.p. 292° is obtained in the same way as above.

To sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide (10.7 parts) taken in 21 parts of cresol and heated to 150° methyl sulphocyanide (4 parts) was gradually added and the heating continued for 1 hour more at 180°. The reaction mixture was treated as in the previous examples and *p*-aminobenzene sulphonycyanamide, m.p. 292° obtained as in the previous cases.

The paper is based on a pending patent application.

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